

NUMERICAL STUDY ON CHARRING PROPERTIES OF ENGINEERED BAMBOO

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ABSTRACT

Fire is one of the most frequent disasters in the world. As bamboo is combustible material, its fire performance greatly limited its structural application. However, study shows that fire safety of bamboo structures can be ensured through reasonable fire design. In this paper, the charring properties of two types of engineered bamboo: laminated bamboo and bamboo scrimber were carefully investigated through numerical study with commercial software ABAQUS. Charring rate was calculated from the simulated 300°C isotherm. The influence of cross-section dimension, fire duration on the charring rate was studied. Two types of engineered bamboo showed similar development rule of charring rate. The charring rate of engineered bamboo decreased slightly with the increase of fire duration.

KEYWORDS

Engineered bamboo; Charring properties; Numerical simulation; Fire duration

INTRODUCTION

Bamboo is a fast-growing material which can grown up in 4 to 6 years. In the process of growth, it can store carbon dioxide and improve the environment. During the whole life cycle of growth, processing, construction, use, maintenance and waste treatment, bamboo is a kind of green and environmentally friendly material. Bamboo products has been widely used as finishing building material. Studies conducted by Sharma et al. (2015a,2015b), Mahdavi et al. (2011), and Li et al. (2013) have shown that engineered bamboo products has a number of advantages as a construction material, and material properties of engineered bamboo are comparable or superior to those of many timber and timber-based products. More and more engineered bamboo products have now been applied as structural materials in practical construction.

Two examples of established engineered bamboo products are laminated bamboo and bamboo scrimber, as shown in Figure 1. Laminated bamboo is composed of longitudinally arranged slender bamboo strips joined with adhesive. The bamboo culm is split, planed, processed, laminated and pressed to form the laminated bamboo board product, and them compressed into required cross-section. In contrast, bamboo scrimber, also referred to as strand woven or parallel strand bamboo (PSB), is made of crushed fiber bundles saturated in resin and compressed into a dense block. The process maintains the longitudinal orientation of the bamboo fibers and utilizes the resin matrix to connect the fiber bundles. Standard has also been published or being compiled related to these products.

(a) Laminated bamboo board

(b) Bamboo scrimber block

Figure 1: Examples of established engineered bamboo products

As bamboo is combustible material, its fire performance is one of the most important factors for application in building construction. Like timber structures, residual cross-section method is commonly suggested to be used in fire design of engineered bamboo structures, which highlight the importance to determine the charring rate of engineered bamboo. The combustion and charring performance of laminated bamboo board was studied by Mena et al. (2012), and the laminated bamboo board was found to satisfy the fire performance requirement as structural and indoor finishing building material. The combustion and charring performance of laminated bamboo and bamboo scrimber were carefully studied by Xu et al. (2016) through cone calorimeter tests, and it was concluded that laminated bamboo and bamboo scrimber showed comparable charring performance to representative softwood and hardwood performance, respectively. The performance of engineered bamboo beams exposed to three-sided standard fire was studied by Chen et al. (2019), charring rate of both laminated bamboo and bamboo scrimber was also presented. The charring properties of bamboo scrimber was investigated by Cui et al. (2020) through standard fire tests, parameters including cross-section dimension, fire duration and exposure surface number were considered, and the notional charring rate considering the corner rounding effect is suggested to be taken as 0.7 mm/min.

In this paper a numerical model was developed to study the temperature distribution of engineered bamboo, and the charring properties was obtained from the temperature distribution.

NUMERICAL SIMULATION MODEL

In this study, the finite element package ABAQUS was used to investigate the charring properties of engineered bamboo. The heat transfer analysis was first conducted to obtain the temperature distribution of the specimen. Then the charring rate was calculated from the simulated 300°C isotherm. Both types of laminated bamboo and bamboo scrimber were studied. The temperature distribution analysis is performed independently of the structural analysis by using heat transfer analysis in ABAQUS.

Finite element type and mesh

An eight-node linear heat transfer solid element (DC3D8) was used for the engineered bamboo beams. Figure 2 illustrates the finite element mesh used in the simulation. Fine mesh is suggested to be used as the temperature may have sudden change in the pyrolysis zone.

(a) Laminated bamboo

(b) Bamboo scrimber

Figure 2: Finite element mesh of engineered bamboo beams

Thermal properties

The variation of thermal properties with temperature was considered in the simulation and these values were taken from reference Xia (2017) and Xiang (2016).

Thermal conductivity

The variation of thermal conductivity of laminated bamboo and bamboo scrimber (referred as LB and BS respectively in Figures 3-5) with temperature was illustrated in Figure 3. The thermal conductivity of two types of engineered bamboo shows similar variation rule, which was observed to increase with temperature in the temperature range of 20 °C~100 °C, and decrease with temperature when the temperature ranges from 100 °C to 280 °C. The value of thermal conductivity of bamboo scrimber was slightly higher than that of laminated bamboo.

Specific heat

As shown in Figure 4, the specific heat of laminated bamboo was observed to increase linearly with temperature in the temperature range of 20 °C~60 °C, and decrease linearly with temperature when the temperature ranges from 60 °C to 100 °C, and then decrease slightly with temperature when the temperature is between 100 °C and 280 °C. The specific heat of bamboo scrimber was observed to increase linearly with temperature in the temperature range of 20 °C~100 °C, and decrease linearly with temperature when the temperature ranges from 100 °C to 120 °C, and then generally keep constant when the temperature is between 120 °C and 300 °C. The peak value of specific heat of bamboo scrimber was greatly higher than that of laminated bamboo.

Figure 3: Variation of thermal conductivity of engineered bamboo with temperature

Figure 4: Variation of specific heat of engineered bamboo with temperature

Density

Figure 5 illustrates the degradation of density with temperature of two types of engineered bamboo. For laminated bamboo, the reduction factor of density was observed to be constant in the temperature range of 20 °C to 100 °C, and decrease greatly with temperature when the temperature ranges from 180 °C to 400 °C, because of the pyrolysis of phenolic resin and the decomposition of glued bamboo fiber. For Bamboo scrimber, the density began to decrease when the temperature in is in the range of 85 °C~110 °C, due to the evaporation of free water and further decrease with temperature when the temperature ranges from 300 °C to 400 °C. The degradation rule of density of bamboo scrimber and laminated bamboo was generally similar.

Figure 5: Variation of reduction factor of density of engineered bamboo with temperature

2.3 Interaction

The convection coefficient of the surfaces exposed to fire was taken as $25 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$ while that of other surfaces was $9 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$. The emissivity coefficient was taken as 0.8. The measured furnace temperature development with time was applied as the ambient temperature in the analysis for validation and ISO 834 standard fire temperature development with time was employed in the parametric analysis.

2.4 Validation

In reference Chen et al. (2019), fire test were conducted on both laminated bamboo and bamboo scrimber beams. The geometry, fire duration of the specimens and measured charring depth were listed in Table 1. The density of laminated bamboo and bamboo scrimber was 663kg/m^3 , 984kg/m^3 with the moisture content 15.2%, 9.2%, respectively. The degradation of thermal conductivity, specific heat and the reduction factor of density were taken as mentioned in section 2.2.

The predicted temperature distribution of the laminated bamboo and bamboo scrimber specimens was shown in Figure 6 and Figure 7 respectively.

(a) 10min

(b) 25min

Figure 6: Temperature distribution of laminated bamboo

(a) 10min

(b) 25min

Figure 7: Temperature distribution of bamboo scrimber

It can be observed from Figures 6 and 7 that laminated bamboo and bamboo scrimber show similar temperature distribution rule. The temperature difference gradient along the cross-section is large for both laminated bamboo and bamboo scrimber beams, and the temperature gradually decreases from outside to inside. The temperature of the fire exposed surface is close to the furnace temperature, while the temperature of interior area is significantly lower due to the protection of the charring layer with much lower thermal conductivity. With the increase of fire duration, the cross-section temperature rises differently, and the closer to the fire exposed surface, the faster the temperature rises. Due to the fact that the fire exposed surface affected by direct thermal radiation and convection, the temperature of fire exposed surface raise rapidly, while for interior area of the cross-section, the temperature rise is relatively slow because the heat is gradually transferred to the interior area through heat conduction.

When the engineered bamboo beam is subjected to fire on three sides, the cross-section isotherm is distributed in a U-shape, and the longer the fire duration is, the smaller the effective section of the engineered bamboo beam is, and the more obvious the U-shaped corner is. The isotherm distribution of the engineering bamboo beam is similar to the shape of the charring line of the specimen after actual fire. It can be concluded that the simulated temperature distribution rule is similar to the practical temperature distribution rule.

From the previous studies (Xu et al., 2016; Chen et al., 2019), the cross-section of engineered bamboo after fire can be divided into three zones, namely, charring layer, pyrolysis zone and normal zone. The boundary line between charring layer and pyrolysis zone is called charring line. Previous study shows that 300 °C can be used as the charring line temperature of engineered bamboo. The comparison between the calculated charring depth and the test results is shown in Table 1. It can be seen from the table that the simulated charring depth is close to the test value. The charring depth of bamboo scrimber is slightly lower than that of laminated bamboo, which may be attributed to the greater density of bamboo scrimber. For engineered bamboo beams exposed to three-sided fire, the charring depth along the horizontal direction is slightly lower than the charring depth along the vertical direction.

Table 1: Comparison between the simulated charring depth and the test results

Specimen No.	Geometry / (mm×mm)	Furnace fire duration / min	Equivalent fire duration / min	Charring depth / mm				Average error %
				Test value		Simulation value		
				D_b	D_h	D_b	D_h	
LGBA-1	100×225	10	15	8	12	7.9	12.0	-0.5
LGBA-2		25	30	22	31	22.5	25.8	-8.9
SGBA-1	100×140	10	15	3	12	6.3	9.3	4.0
SGBA-2		25	30	15	23	18.8	20.8	4.2

Note: D_b and D_h denote the charring depth along horizontal and vertical direction respectively.

PARAMETRIC STUDY

From the validation in section 2.4, the heat transfer analysis model developed in this paper has been proved can be used to predict the charring properties of engineered bamboo. Therefore, parametric study was conducted using the developed model to further study the charring properties of engineered bamboo. As the laminated bamboo and bamboo scrimber shows similar variation with geometry and fire duration, only laminated bamboo was considered in this study. Parameters including geometry, fire duration were considered and summarized in Table 2. The simulated temperature distribution was presented in Figures 8 and 9. Figure 10 shows the temperature distribution along two directions for different fire duration. The obtained charring depth and charring rate is listed in Table 2. It is worth to note that the average charring rate in Table 2 does consider the influence of round effect.

Figure 8: Simulated temperature distribution of laminated bamboo with cross-section of 150×300

Figure 9: Simulated temperature distribution of laminated bamboo with cross-section of 200×400

Figure 10: Simulated temperature development of laminated bamboo with cross-section of 150 ×300

Figure 11: Simulated temperature development of laminated bamboo with cross-section of 200×400

Table 2: Summarize of the simulation results from parametric study

Specimens No.	Geometry / (mm×mm)	Fire duration (min)	Charring depth (mm)			Average charring rate / (mm/min)
			D_b	D_h	Average	
LGBA-150-1	150×300	15	9	13	11.0	0.73
LGBA-150-2		30	19	24	21.5	0.72
LGBA-150-3		60	40	45	42.5	0.71
LGBA-200-1	200×400	15	9	13	11.0	0.73
LGBA-200-2		30	19	24	21.5	0.72
LGBA-200-3		45	30	35	32.5	0.71
LGBA-200-4		60	39	44	41.5	0.69

Note: D_b and D_h denote the charring depth along horizontal and vertical direction respectively.

It can be observed from Table 2 that the cross-section dimension has slight influence on the charring rate of engineered bamboo. However, when the width of the beam less than 80 mm after fire, the charring rate of beams with smaller cross-section dimension is slightly larger due to the influence of fire exposure for two directions. The charring rate of engineered bamboo decreases slightly with the increase of fire duration.

CONCLUSION

A finite element model was proposed in this paper to study the charring properties of engineered bamboo. The model was firstly validated with test results, and good agreement was observed in the comparison between the predicted and measured result. Then the developed model was used to conduct parametric study to further investigate the influence of geometry and fire duration on the charring properties of laminated bamboo.

The main conclusions are summarized as follows:

1 When the engineered bamboo beam is subjected to fire on three sides, the cross-section isotherm is distributed in a U-shape due to the round effect at the corners.

2 Laminated bamboo and bamboo scrimber shows similar temperature distribution rule. The charring rate of bamboo scrimber is lower than that of laminated bamboo.

3 The cross-section dimension has slight influence on the charring rate of engineered bamboo. However, when the width of the beam less than 80 mm after fire, the charring rate of beams with smaller cross-section dimension is slightly larger. The charring rate of engineered bamboo decreased slightly with the increase of fire duration.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.